

Youth Festivals, Culture, and Brotherhood

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Abstract

Youth festivals are promoting art and culture. Students learn competitive nature during the festivals. Youth festival promotes brotherhood, national unity, and mutual respect. The main objective of the study is to know the association between geographical background of respondents and their opinion on culture and leadership qualities promotion. We did content analysis to collect data. We used codebook to categorize the variables. Result indicates that respondents think that the programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. Urban and rural respondents agreed that youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.

Keywords: Social-media, Social awareness, Communication, Leadership qualities, and geographical spread.

1.0 Introduction

Youth festivals promote culture and the arts. They are important in academic routines, from schools and colleges to districts and states. This competition showcases dance, music, painting, modeling, writing, mimes, and theatre. Students can showcase their writing and art at festivals (*Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports, 2022*). Contests at the youth festival give an avenue to foster mutual respect, social peace, national unity, and compassion. Additionally, it fosters the cultural growth of a nation and a sense of fraternity among pupils.

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Festivals for youth foster community cohesion and place youth at the center of the cultural and social milieu. They are also a means of intergenerational communication and cultural education. In addition, they serve a crucial role in safeguarding cultural heritage by transmitting information and experiences to future generations (Owusu-Frempong, 2005).

The youth festival provides a vibrant venue for exchanging ideas, making new friends, and enjoying films, music, and workshops. It offers a variety of educational options for children, adolescents, schools, and enterprises in the communication and media literacy field. Youth festivals are a thorough and enthusiastic celebration of media, serving as a dynamic communication platform for the promotion of media culture.

1.1 festival, tradition, and fraternity

Art and culture are the foundation of international harmony. Art is the reflection of society, which is the representation of people's lives. Creativity fundamentally affects the human heart and elicits diverse aesthetic feelings in individuals. Art may provoke a range of feelings, and these sentiments can readily influence individuals worldwide. Youth festivals are organized in India alongside the Union Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports and State Governments to find artistic talent.

The primary purpose of youth festivals is to foster artistic and cultural growth. They have gained importance in the academic routine at all levels, from school and college to district and state levels. This competition highlights a variety of arts and civilizations, including dance, music, painting, modeling, writing, mimes, and theatre. Such activities allow students to showcase their literary and artistic abilities. It gives the youth a new sense of energy (*Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports, 2022*).

Only by promoting brotherhood throughout the nation can violence, collectivism, and classism be eradicated. It is also required for global peace. National unity is crucial for the integrity of the country, worldwide progress, and brotherhood. Since ancient times, India has been famed for its art, culture, and fraternity. The foundation of Indian culture is the philosophy of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*. This term appears in verse 74 of chapter 4 of the *Mahaupanishad* and the *Bhagavad Gita* (Kiran, 2018).

The prosperous Indian culture has been transformed by the numerous fairs and festivals held throughout the country. These festivals have been held for a long time to attract tourists. This study investigates how these festivals can draw tourists to India for economic development and the preservation of historical culture (Dutta & Durgamohan, 2016).

2.0 Review of literature

Among the most significant aspects of research is reviewing the relevant research or literature review. The literature evaluation reflects the current state of studies on the subject and opens the way to future research opportunities.

Kristiansen et al. (2016) studied the 12th European Youth Olympic Festival in Austria and Liechtenstein in January 2015. The researchers identified key and secondary stakeholders based on the effect on event planning, implementation, and impact and examined co-hosting obstacles and issues. The European Youth Olympic Festival needed more formal funding and event. Local stakeholders benefited the most and were prepared to pay. The planning team featured regional funders, businesses, and organizations as key participants, while involvement was limited for PWB core interested parties. The European Youth Olympic Festival may have a small influence, but it might have a lasting impact on its co-hosts. Co-facilitating is an excellent strategy for prospective Olympic organizers who seek to engage tiny nations and reap the benefits of reduced costs, strengthened communities, and cross-border ties.

Packer & Ballantyne (2011) used positive psychology to describe how music festivals affect teenage festival attendees' psychological and social well-being. Positive psychology theory was used to identify four music festival well-being outcomes. A conceptual model is also offered to guide relevant research. This strategy lets organizers and attendees maximize the psychological and social benefits of music festivals for young adults.

Koivunen's (2014) study of the World Youth Festival examines the meaning of competition in Soviet culture during the 1940s and 1950s. Culture and competitiveness shaped communist utopias. The Soviet mission was based on a cultural alternative to capitalism and many ideological and economic foundations. The Soviet Union's cultural supremacy began in the 1930s with the concept that it was the "real guardian" of European classical heritage, unlike the West's demoralized and commercialized culture.

3.0 Methodology: The present part of the study contains objectives, hypothesis, research design and sample design.

3.1 Objectives: Objectives of the study as follows-

RO1: To know the association between geographical background of respondents and the statement 'The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with

their local culture.’

RO2: To find out the association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.’

RO3: To find out the association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.’

RO4: To analyze the association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.’

3.2 Hypothesis: The testable hypothesis of the present study is as follows:

Ha1: There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture.’

Ha2: There is an association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.’

Ha3: There is an association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.’

Ha4: There is an association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.’

3.3 Research design: The present study is a description. We did a cross-sectional study to get information from the whole population. We used a survey method with a closed-ended questionnaire to get the information we needed.

3.4 Design of the sample and duration of the study: Part of the population for this study is made up of university students and teachers. With the help of the purposive sampling method, we got samples from four universities in Haryana and Punjab. We got information from October to December of 2022 from the respondents.

4.0 Analysis: We analysis variable based on crosstabulation to know the association between two or more variables.

4.1: Association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture.’

Geographical background of respondents	The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture.				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Urban	6.0%	7.0%	12.9%	27.9%	46.3%
Semi-urban	7.3%	7.3%	14.6%	17.1%	53.7%
Rural	5.1%	5.1%	5.1%	28.8%	55.9%
Total	6.0%	6.5%	11.0%	25.9%	50.6%

Table 4.1: Crosstabulation between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture.’

During the youth festival, multiple cultures unite on a same stage and demonstrate diversity within unity. Throughout the festival, the youth participate in a variety of recreational and challenging events. Table 4.1 indicates that 46.3% of urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. 27.9% respondents agree, 12.9% neutral, 7.0% disagree, and 6.0% are strongly disagree. On the other hand, 53.7% of semi-urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. 17.1% respondents agree, 14.6% neutral, 7.3% disagree, and 7.3% are strongly disagree. Consequently, 55.9% of rural respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. 28.8% respondents agree, 5.1% neutral, 5.1% disagree, and 5.1% are strongly disagree. Overall, 50.6% of respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. 25.8% respondents agree, 11.0% neutral, 6.5% disagree, and 6.0% are strongly disagree with the statement.

4.2: Association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the

various cultures and arts of the country.’

Geographical background of respondents	The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Urban	13.9%	7.0%	10.9%	37.8%	30.3%
Semi-urban	7.3%	9.8%	7.3%	34.1%	41.5%
Rural	1.7%	10.2%	11.9%	35.6%	40.7%
Total	9.0%	8.5%	10.5%	36.4%	35.7%

Table 4.2: Crosstabulation between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.’

Using a comprehensive and interactive approach, university-hosted youth festivals combine many cultures in a single thread. Table 4.2 indicates that 30.3% of urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. 37.8% respondents agree, 10.9% neutral, 7.0% disagree, and 13.9% are strongly disagree. On the other hand, 41.5% of semi-urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. 34.1% respondents agree, 7.3% neutral, 9.8% disagree, and 7.3% are strongly disagree. Consequently, 40.7% of rural respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. 35.6% respondents agree, 11.9% neutral, 10.2% disagree, and 1.7% are strongly disagree. Overall, 35.7% of respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. 36.4% respondents agree, 10.5% neutral, 8.5% disagree, and 9.0% are strongly disagree with the statement.

4.3: Association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.’

Geographical background of	The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.
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respondents	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Urban	20.4%	22.9%	17.9%	19.9%	18.9%
Semi-urban	39.0%	17.1%	19.5%	9.8%	14.6%
Rural	22.0%	42.4%	13.6%	11.9%	10.2%
Total	24.7%	27.4%	17.0%	15.5%	15.5%

Table 4.3: Crosstabulation between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.’

Youth festival is a cultural event meant to foster emotional connections between youth. Under this, efforts are made to enhance the legacy's aesthetic. Table 4.3 indicates that 18.9% of urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level. 19.9% respondents agree, 17.9% neutral, 22.9% disagree, and 20.4% are strongly disagree. On the other hand, 14.6% of semi-urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level. 9.8% respondents agree, 19.5% neutral, 17.1% disagree, and 39.0% are strongly disagree. Consequently, 10.2% of rural respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level. 11.9% respondents agree, 13.6% neutral, 42.4% disagree, and 22.0% are strongly disagree. Overall, 15.5% of respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. 15.5% respondents agree, 17.0% neutral, 27.4% disagree, and 24.7% are strongly disagree with the statement.

4.4: Association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.’

Geographical background of respondents	Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Urban	9.0%	4.0%	10.0%	33.8%	43.3%

Semi-urban	7.3%	2.4%	12.2%	31.7%	46.3%
Rural	1.7%	5.1%	3.4%	35.6%	54.2%
Total	6.5%	4.0%	8.5%	33.9%	47.1%

Table 4.4: Crosstabulation between geographical background of respondents and the statement 'Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.'

The diverse relational solidarity created by the cultural activities at the youth festival plays a crucial role in the formation of youth identity. Table 4.4 indicates that 43.3% of urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival. 33.8% respondents agree, 10.0% neutral, 4.0% disagree, and 9.0% are strongly disagree. On the other hand, 46.3% of semi-urban respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival. 31.7% respondents agree, 12.2% neutral, 2.4% disagree, and 7.3% are strongly disagree. Consequently, 54.2% of rural respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival. 35.6% respondents agree, 3.4% neutral, 5.1% disagree, and 1.7% are strongly disagree. Overall, 47.1% of respondents are strongly agree with the statement that the leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival. 33.9% respondents agree, 8.5% neutral, 4.0% disagree, and 6.5% are strongly disagree with the statement.

4.5: Association between geographical background of respondents and the statement 'The most trusted media for you to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities.'

Geographical background of respondents	The most trusted media for you to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities.			
	Social Media	News Portals	Radio-TV	Newspapers/ Magazines
Urban	61.7%	10.0%	2.0%	26.4%
Semi-urban	48.8%	9.8%	4.9%	36.6%
Rural	45.8%	18.6%	11.9%	23.7%
Total	54.4%	12.5%	5.5%	27.7%

Table 4.5: Crosstabulation between geographical background of respondents and the

statement ‘The most trusted media for you to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities.’

Media channels and sources must be trustworthy. Their purity impacts the reader, the listener, and society as a whole. Table 4.5 indicates that 61.7% of urban respondents consider that social media is the most trusted media to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities. 26.4% respondents believe newspapers/magazines, 10.0% think news portals, and 2.0% consider Radio-TV as trusted media. On the other hand, 48.8% of semi-urban respondents consider that social media is the most trusted media to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities. 36.6% respondents believe newspapers/magazines, 9.8% think news portals, and 4.9% consider radio-TV as trusted media. Consequently, 45.8% of rural respondents consider that social media is the most trusted media to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities. 23.7% respondents believe newspapers/magazines, 18.6% think news portals, and 11.9% consider radio-TV as trusted media. Overall, 54.4% of respondents consider that social media is the most trusted media to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities. 27.7% respondents believe newspapers/magazines, 12.5% think news portals, and 5.5% consider radio-TV as trusted media.

4.6 Hypothesis testing: Chi-Squire test

Ho1: There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture.’

Pearson Chi-Square	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
	11.061 ^a	8	.198

There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture’ because p-value 0.198 is more than the significance value 0.05. Hence, we failed to reject the null hypothesis i.e. “There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture.’”

Ho2: There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.’

Pearson Chi-Square	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
	18.298 ^a	8	.019

There is an association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country’ because p-value 0.019 is less than the significance value 0.05. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis i.e. “There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.’”

Ho3: There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.’

Pearson Chi-Square	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
	33.204 ^a	8	.000

There is an association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level’ because p-value 0.000 is less than the significance value 0.05. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis i.e. “There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.’”

Ho4: There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.’

Pearson Chi-Square	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
	14.580 ^a	8	.068

There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival’ because p-value 0.068 is more than the significance value 0.05. Hence, we failed to reject the null hypothesis i.e. “There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.’”

5.0 Result:

Almost half of urban respondents strongly agree, and one-fourth of respondents agree that the programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. On the other hand, half of semi-urban respondents strongly agree, and less than one-fourth of respondents agree that the programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. Consequently, more than half of rural respondents strongly agree, and more than one-fourth of respondents agree that the programs organized during the Youth Festival help the youth to connect with their local culture. The majority of individuals with a neutral opinion about the statement are urban respondents.

More than one-fourth of urban respondents strongly agree, and one-thirds of respondents agree that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. On the other hand, less than half of semi-urban respondents strongly agree, and more than one-thirds of respondents agree that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. Consequently, less than half of rural respondents strongly agree, and more than one-thirds of respondents agree that the events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country. The number of rural respondents who strongly disagree is negligible. The majority of individuals with a neutral opinion about the statement are rural respondents.

Less than one-fourth of urban respondents strongly disagree, and less than one-fourth of respondents disagree that the program of youth festival does not communicate the art and

culture of the youth at the global level. On the other hand, more than one-thirds of semi-urban respondents strongly disagree, and less than one-fourth of respondents disagree that the program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level. Consequently, less than one fourth of rural respondents strongly disagree, and less than half of respondents disagree that the program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level. The majority of individuals with a neutral opinion about the statement are semi-urban respondents.

Less than half of urban respondents strongly agree, and one-thirds of respondents agree that the leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival. On the other hand, less than half of semi-urban respondents strongly agree, and almost one-thirds of respondents agree that the leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival. Consequently, more than half of rural respondents strongly agree, and one-thirds of respondents agree that the leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival. The number of disagree urban, semi-urban and strongly disagree rural respondents is negligible. The majority of individuals with a neutral opinion about the statement are semi-urban respondents.

Almost two-thirds of urban respondents consider that social media is the most trusted media to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities. While more than one-fourth of respondents recognize newspaper/magazines as most trusted media. on the other hand, almost half of semi-urban respondents consider that social media is the most trusted media to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities. While one-thirds of respondents recognize newspaper/magazines as most trusted media. Consequently, almost half of rural respondents consider that social media is the most trusted media to know about the youth festival organized in Indian universities. While less than one-fourth of respondents recognize newspaper/magazines as most trusted media. less than one-fourth of respondents believe news portals as most trusted media. The number of urban respondents who regard radio/TV as a credible medium is insignificant. Rural are more among the respondents who consider radio/TV as a reliable medium.

There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement 'The programs organized during the youth festival help the youth to connect with their local culture.'

There is an association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The events held during the youth festival create awareness among the youth about the various cultures and arts of the country.’

There is an association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘The program of youth festival does not communicate the art and culture of the youth at the global level.’

There is no association between geographical background of respondents and the statement ‘Leadership qualities develop in the youth during the youth festival.’

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